

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

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PARCroute roadmap1

WP 2 – T2.2

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

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Responsible author(s)	Matthias Herzler, BfR, matthias.herzler@bfr.bund.de Isabella Apruzzese, BfR, isabella.apruzzese@bfr.bund.de Gabriele Flingelli, BfR, gabriele.flingelli@bfr.bund.de Sónia Namorado, INSA, sonia.namorado@insa.min-saude.pt
Co-authors	Nicole Bandow, UBA, Nicole.Bandow@uba.de Aleksandra Cavoski, UOB, a.cavoski@bham.ac.uk John Colbourne, UOB, j.k.colbourne@bham.ac.uk Laura Holden, UOB, l.holden.1@bham.ac.uk Romana Hornek-Gausterer, EAA, romana.hornek-gausterer@umweltbundesamt.at Andreas-Marius Kaiser, EAA, andreas.kaiser@umweltbundesamt.at Robert Lee, UOB, r.g.lee@bham.ac.uk Joana Lobo Vicente, EEA, joana.lobo@eea.europa.eu Eleonora Longhin, NILU, eml@nilu.no Peter von der Ohe, UBA, peter.vonderohe@uba.de Maria Uhl, EAA, maria.uhl@umweltbundesamt.at
Reviewers	Mirjam Luijten, RIVM, mirjam.luijten@rivm.nl Georges Kass, EFSA, georges.kass@efsa.europa.eu
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Abstract

Although there has been significant progress in the development of “New Approach Methodologies” (NAMs), almost all major chemical legislations in Europe rely substantially on animal testing. One of the goals of the Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals (PARC) is to promote “Next- Generation Risk Assessment” (NGRA), to replace *in vivo* testing in the future. Within PARC, we develop *NGRAroute*, the concrete proposal for a roadmap towards implementation of NGRA as the default risk assessment approach in various EU chemical legislations, in line with the goals of the European Commission’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS).

Here we share a first overview of the current status of the roadmap development (as per end of February 2023). The basic preparatory work for this roadmap is currently ongoing (and is planned to be completed by June 2023), including a review of existing work on NGRA and its contextual domains and a mapping of relevant EU chemical legislations with respect to risk assessment workflows, associated risk assessment questions, and an analysis of how these could be transformed to NGRA. Moreover, a collaboration has been established with the Horizon 2020 cluster ASPIS (Animal-free Safety assessment of chemicals: Project cluster for Implementation of novel Strategies). Within the ASPIS cluster, the project RISK-HUNT3R is currently developing an NGRA strategy framework, which will provide the structural basis for the further roadmap work and, ultimately, a concrete and structured proposal for how NGRA could be implemented in the various EU chemical legislations.

In the next phase, a “science-to-policy dialogue” (S2PD) network will be built to directly involve European and global stakeholders from the research, regulatory and policy domains, who have a key role in applying and changing the existing chemical regulations, in the discussions. This will ensure that the roadmap will ultimately represent a broad consensus within the chemical risk assessment community.

Key Words

Chemicals; Environmental Risk Assessment; Human Health Risk Assessment; Next-Generation Risk Assessment; NAMs; NGRA; Roadmap

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2. Abbreviations and acronyms

ASPIS	Animal-free Safety assessment of chemicals: Project cluster for Implementation of novel Strategies
CRA	Chemical Risk Assessment
DASS	Defined Approach(es) for Skin Sensitisation
EU	European Union
IATA	Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment
NAMs	New Approach Methodologies
NGRA	Next-Generation Risk Assessment
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development
PARC	Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
S2PD	Science-to-Policy Dialogue
WP	Work package

3. Introduction to the interim report

Overview

This document reports the progress made during PARC year 1 by PARC Task 2.2 (T 2.2) on the development of *NGRAroute*, the roadmap to support the regulatory uptake of Next-Generation Risk Assessment (NGRA). It focuses on the preliminary work required for the roadmap and it is intended to be the basis for future discussions. The information on the NGRA roadmap described in this document describes the approach undertaken by T 2.2 so far, and the ideas presented here will certainly be subject to future changes.

Background

PARCroute is a horizontal project, which will develop and oversee, in a joint effort with the other work packages (WPs) within PARC, the implementation of strategic roadmaps in order to actively promote the uptake of the innovative science developed in PARC into regulatory chemical risk assessment (CRA)¹ practice.

This work will be based on the systematic identification of

- gaps/innovation needs of the current regulatory practice,
- the characterisation of specific innovation goals,
- the identification of the optimal update process,
- the regulatory key players (e.g., certain regulatory bodies, for example the meeting of the Competent Authorities for REACH and CLP, CARACAL) involved in that process and
- the resources needed and timelines involved to achieve it.

PARCroute will align PARC with the research agenda of the European Union (EU) Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability² which provides the general strategic framework. It will kick off by developing “*NGRAroute*”, a roadmap for actively promoting the paradigm shift towards implementing NGRA in the major EU chemical regulation programmes. Other roadmaps might follow in the years to come, in collaboration with the relevant PARC WPs (and depending on further initiatives from the Partnership).

¹ It is noted that chemical risk assessment includes hazard identification, hazard characterisation, exposure assessment, and risk characterisation (i.e. the comparison of exposure with a quantitative measure of hazard). In this report, the term “CRA” is meant to also include assessments which do not contain all of these elements. For example, classification and labelling of a hazardous chemical under Regulation (EC) 1272/2008 (The CLP Regulation) only includes hazard assessment, but would be subsumed under “CRA” as well.

² https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/chemicals-strategy_en (last accessed 2023-04-29)

Structure of the roadmap development

The schematic steps for the development of *NGRAroute* are to

1. spell out the *NGRAroute* vision and scope;
2. map the “NGRA topology” (a map of related aspects of NGRA);
3. perform a focused bibliographic research on existing NGRA publications and activities;
4. develop a generalised regulatory NGRA framework/workflow;
5. identify gaps and obstacles and develop recommendations for how to overcome them;
6. develop a strategy with realistic, but concrete timelines and methods for transitioning to NGRA to be proposed to the policy level and, lastly,
7. finalise the roadmap document.

The timeline for the development of the roadmap is available in section 8. At the time of drafting of this report, steps 1, 2 and 3 have been initiated, discussions are ongoing and the respective progress is described in the following sub-sections.

Regarding step 4, a comparable activity for the development of a human health-related NGRA strategy framework is being developed under the ASPIS cluster (Animal-free Safety assessment of chemicals: Project cluster for Implementation of novel Strategies)³, more specifically, under the RISK-HUNT3R⁴ project. Given that several PARC partners, including from WPs 5, 6 and from Task 2.2, are actively contributing to this activity, discussions are currently ongoing how synergies can be best realised by sharing the work in the most efficient way. For example, the practical development of the strategy framework may be better placed in RISK-HUNT3R, which will carry out a number of case studies to further elaborate on specific aspects of the framework. However, activities towards its regulatory uptake might then be better placed under PARC Task 2.2, which will offer a broader network and larger platform for engaging all relevant stakeholders and ensure the integration of further risk assessment aspects concerning human health and the environment.

A workable version of the RISK-HUNT3R NGRA strategy framework is currently tentatively expected towards the end of 2023, which would still allow its integration into *NGRAroute*. Moreover, the initial work on the NGRA strategy framework has shown that the creation of such a framework is a complex task, which could not have been performed by Task 2.2 alone within a comparable time frame. Similar frameworks have been proposed (e.g. recently by Magurany et al.⁵) or may be developed in the near future and the overall integration of these frameworks will be a matter of further work under *NGRAroute*.

³ <https://aspis-cluster.eu> (last accessed 2023-04-29)

⁴ <https://www.risk-hunt3r.eu> (last accessed 2023-04-29)

⁵ Magurany KA et al. (2023); DOI: [10.1093/toxsci/kfad012](https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfad012)

It is further noted that, to the best knowledge of the authors of this report, a similarly elaborated framework for environmental risk assessment is currently not available. Whether this can be developed by/under Task 2.2 – and also possible implications for the overall timeline for *NGRAroute* - will be a matter of further discussion.

Why a roadmap?

Although substantial progress has been made with the development of so-called “New Approach Methodologies” (NAMs), especially in the field of human health, practically all major chemical regulations in Europe requiring CRA – with the exception of the Cosmetics Regulation – still strongly rely on animal testing.

At the same time, it is increasingly recognised that traditional CRA workflows, such as the ones implemented under the REACH Regulation, are only able to procure relevant safety information on a limited number of chemicals within a reasonable amount of time, using a high number of experimental animals and financial and personal resources in both industry and authorities (cf. e.g. Kavlock et al., 2018)⁶.

More than a decade ago, the United States Environment Protection Agency (US EPA) initiated conceptual work on the “Next Generation (NexGen) of Risk Assessment” as a systematic approach to overcome these problems, documented in the pivotal report “Next Generation Risk Assessment: Incorporation of Recent Advances in Molecular, Computational, and Systems Biology”⁷.

In addition, the Tox21 program⁸, a joint effort of several U.S. federal agencies, can be considered a positive example for structuring the process of introducing a paradigm change in science-based CRA, starting with a dedicated roadmap in 2004⁹, laying out a more detailed vision and strategy in the landmark report “Toxicity Testing in the 21st Century. A Vision and a Strategy” published by the U.S. National Academy of Sciences in 2007¹⁰ and followed by a formal installation of the alliance of the involved U.S. agencies in 2008¹¹. Over the past 15 years, this co-operation has been further developed strategically and scientifically^{12,13}

⁶ Kavlock R et al. (2018); DOI: [10.1021/acs.chemrestox.7b00339](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemrestox.7b00339))

⁷ <https://cfpub.epa.gov/ncea/risk/recordisplay.cfm?deid=286690> (last accessed 2023-04-29)

⁸ <https://tox21.gov> (last accessed 2023-04-29)

⁹ https://ntp.niehs.nih.gov/ntp/about_ntp/ntpvision/ntproadmap_508.pdf (last accessed 2023-04-29)

¹⁰ <https://nap.nationalacademies.org/catalog/11970/toxicity-testing-in-the-21st-century-a-vision-and-a-strategy> (last accessed 2023-04-29)

¹¹ <https://www.nih.gov/news-events/news-releases/nih-collaborates-epa-improve-safety-testing-chemicals> (last accessed 2023-04-29)

¹² Krewski D et al. (2010), DOI: [10.1080/10937404.2010.483176](https://doi.org/10.1080/10937404.2010.483176)

¹³ Thomas R et al. (2018), DOI: [10.14573/altex.1803011](https://doi.org/10.14573/altex.1803011)

providing an unprecedented dynamic for the science-based innovation of CRA. It should, however, be mentioned that the Tox21 strategies and roadmaps so far have mainly focused on establishing the scientific side of 21st century toxicology, whereas a strategy for rolling out these concepts into regulatory CRA on a broad scale has not been developed to the knowledge of the authors of this report¹⁴.

In Europe, major EU projects such as SEURAT-1¹⁵ or EU-ToxRisk¹⁶ have greatly improved our understanding of the potential of NAMs to support regulatory CRA for human health. These projects have achieved great progress on the scientific side and have successfully started addressing (and bridging) the communication gap between academic researchers and regulatory practitioners. Recently, a number of further EU framework programs, such as those organised in the ASPIS cluster (cf. above) and HBM4EU (www.hbm4eu.eu), have been initiated which will build on and complement this successful work.

On a global scale, the Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) has successfully facilitated the conceptual development of innovative chemical hazard and risk assessment methodologies, such as the Defined Approaches for Skin Sensitisation (DASS) Guideline Document 497 published in 2021¹⁷, and, via the “Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment” (IATA) case studies¹⁸ project, continues to explore actively their practical application in the regulatory context. The OECD also plays a key role in further developing concepts and practical approaches to validate test as well as non-test methods regarding their fitness-for-purpose for regulatory CRA.

In addition, not only the large-scale research projects named above (and others), but also regulatory bodies and agencies have started initiatives to actively investigate and promote NAMs and NGRA. As only one important example (out of several), the initiative for “Accelerating the Pace of Chemical Risk Assessment” (APCRA)¹⁹ aims to discuss “*progress and barriers in applying new tools to prioritization, screening, and quantitative risk assessment of differing levels of complexity*” and “*opportunities to increase collaboration in order to accelerate the pace of chemical risk assessments*” by means of case studies with high regulatory relevance²⁰.

¹⁴ It may be speculated that this aspect did not receive as much attention, because the US chemicals legislation in general seems to provide risk assessors with more leeway regarding the choice of methodology acceptable for their risk assessments, compared to EU legislations such as REACH or those on pesticides and biocides, which are based on a more rigid system of information requirements. This is a point to be further followed up on under *NGRAroute*.

¹⁵ <https://www.seurat-1.eu/> (last accessed 2023-04-29)

¹⁶ <https://www.eu-toxrisk.eu/> (last accessed 2023-04-29)

¹⁷ https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/environment/guideline-no-497-defined-approaches-on-skin-sensitisation_b92879a4-en (last accessed 2023-04-29)

¹⁸ <https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/iata/> (last accessed 2023-04-29)

¹⁹ <https://apcra.net> (last accessed 2023-04-29)

²⁰ Cf. e.g. the landmark publication by Paul Friedman K et al. (2019); DOI: [10.1093/toxsci/kfz201](https://doi.org/10.1093/toxsci/kfz201)

Still, despite all these efforts, regulatory implementation of NAMs or “Next-Generation Risk assessment” (NGRA) approaches in EU chemicals legislation has been limited to certain endpoints such as skin sensitisation and skin irritation, where significant progress has been made, while for others it has been slow to negligible.

In 2020, the European Commission has noted in the CSS:

*“Despite a strong EU policy for the **protection of animals used for scientific purposes**, adopted 10 years ago, which makes full replacement of animal testing its ultimate goal, animals are still required to be used systematically for testing in the field of chemicals. **Safety testing and chemical risk assessment** need to innovate in order to reduce dependency on animal testing but also to improve the quality, efficiency and speed of chemical hazard and risk assessments.”*

Scientific, economic and political challenges are associated with the paradigm change towards NGRA, but part of the slow progress in this field may also be attributed to the fact that the strategic conceptualisation of past EU research projects often did not include a concrete implementation plan for the uptake of their findings into CRA practice. As the example of the U.S. Tox21 program has shown, however, a clear **vision**, accompanied by a **strategic roadmap**, can be key factors in finally achieving that paradigm change also in the EU.

Such a roadmap proposal needs to cover all relevant aspects of the implementation process, guided by the following questions:

- What is the current situation, i.e. what is the status of the existing NGRA approaches in terms of scientific development, maturation, validation, and readiness for regulatory applicability? What are the toxicological endpoints covered by existing *in vivo* test guidelines that are most likely to be good candidates for NGRA implementation in the nearer future?
- What are the regulatory needs (i.e. the explicit legal and sub-legal requirements as well as the implicit protection goals)?
- What are the desired outcomes/specific goals (in the case of *NGRAroute*: what does an NGRA framework look like that is able to achieve the regulatory protection goals behind the respective legislation)?
- What are the processes needed to achieve the outcome (what is the process by which this change can be achieved technically, what is the process for changing the legislation and/or associated guidance)?
- Who are the relevant key players, i.e. stakeholders²¹ involved in this process, that are part of the implementation process and therefore have to be included in the discussions?

²¹ E.g. the European Commission, the European agencies, Member State competent authorities, or industry associations

Which regulatory bodies²² have to be approached in this dialogue, in order to convince them to support the implementation of the aspired change?

- What are the chances and odds of success²³, which resources will be needed (and are they available) and what are the timelines associated with the update process?

These considerations are depicted in a generalised way (i.e. related to roadmaps for updating regulatory practice in general) in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.**. Among other things, “Theory of Change”²⁴ models might help in providing a structure for the further work.

Figure 1: Generalised process for updating current regulatory practice via strategic roadmaps developed under PARCroute (for a description of the individual steps, see text). The figure also shows how PARCroute will be connected to the regulatory/policy level, the PARC partnership as a whole and further external partners via a dedicated science-to-policy (S2PD) network (cf. section 7 for details). WP = Work Package, MB = Management Board, GB = Governing Board, GSB = Grant Signatory Board, ASPIS = Animal-free Safety assessment of chemicals: Project cluster for Implementation of novel Strategies, EURION = European Cluster to Improve Identification of Endocrine Disruptors, US EPA = United States Environmental Protection Agency, OECD = Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, CEFIC = European Chemical Industry Council, ECETOC = European Centre for Ecotoxicology and Toxicology of Chemicals.

Next-Generation Environmental Risk Assessment

While the concept of NGRA for human health has already been discussed and elaborated on on various occasions, for environmental risk assessment (ERA) this seems not to be the case to the same extent. In addition, currently, certain aspects of ERA, for example the effects of chemicals and combined exposure on biodiversity are not adequately considered in risk assessment and/or in central pieces of chemical legislations (like REACH and CLP). More research is needed to fill the knowledge gaps, and to foster the integration of biodiversity into

²² E.g. CARACAL, the Scientific Committee for Consumer Safety (SCCS), ECHA’s Risk Assessment Committee (RAC) or EFSA’s Panels on plant protection products and their residues (PPR) or food contact materials, enzymes and processing aids (CEF), to name just a few

²³ In the sense of an analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats (SWOT analysis)

²⁴ Cf. Brest P (2010), <https://sc4ccm.jsi.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/The-Power-Of-Theories-Of-Change.pdf> or Brown M (2020), https://ssir.org/articles/entry/unpacking_the_theory_of_change (both last accessed 2023-04-29)

CRA. Many challenges exist to apply the NGRA approach to the environmental domain, these include chemical mixtures or the effects of climate change that are contributing to the immense loss of biodiversity. In addition, new monitoring approaches and methods are needed to improve exposure assessment. Here PARC, and specifically *NGRAroute*, offer the opportunity to start the development of a concept for Next-Generation Environmental Risk Assessment.

4. *NGRAroute* Vision and Scope

The roadmap to implement NGRA approaches in EU chemical safety legislations (*NGRAroute*) strives to concretely support innovation in traditional human health and environmental CRA, as well as in new fields such as the development of “safe-and-sustainable-by-design” (SSbD) chemicals, another prominently aspect featured in the CSS (section 2.1). For a broad acceptance of its results, the development of *NGRAroute* will involve a network of researchers, regulatory practitioners and policy makers from both within and outside of PARC.

What is NGRA?

One of the tasks of *NGRAroute* is to develop a fully workable, operational definition of NGRA, which is supported by the entire PARC community. Recently, members of the PARC consortium have proposed the following definition:

“In the context of PARC, NGRA refers to the concept of using data from New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) for chemical risk assessment. In its ideal the concept relies on tiered combinations of in silico tools, complex in vitro systems, organ models and omics approaches in conjunction with physiologically based toxicokinetic modelling and complex exposure models. While the concept of NGRA comprises Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) and quantitative AOPs as established tools for hazard assessment, it is not limited to these, nor does it exclude the use of in vivo data or histopathology. However, it puts a strong emphasis on using state-of-the-art systems and as such is predominantly mechanism-driven, and not driven by apical (toxicological) endpoints.”²⁵ (Marx-Stoelting P et al., 2022)

This description already marks a good starting point, but will have to be further elaborated on in the future. Nevertheless, a non-exhaustive list of **principles and elements for a generalised NGRA framework** can be formulated already now, at the onset of this task.

²⁵ Marx-Stoelting P. et al. (2022); DOI: 10.1007/s00204-022-03435-7

A fit-for-purpose NGRA framework such as e.g. the one currently developed under the ASPIS cluster (cf. above):

- **does no longer rely on new *in vivo* testing²⁶** in experimental animals, but uses already existing information in combination with information generated using *in vitro* test systems and *in silico* tools, informed by **mechanistic information** available from **Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs)** demonstrating the relevance of the chemical risk investigated;
- **overcomes the species barrier** by, for example, performing any new *in vitro* testing preferably using tissue from the species for which the risk assessment is conducted provided the information obtained from the test system is fit for purpose (i.e. human tissue in the case of human health risk assessments) and by further developing a methodology to adequately characterise the relevance and uncertainties of such *in vitro* testing results for other species and taxonomic categories;
- needs to provide a **comparable or higher level of protection** for human health and the environment compared to the traditional whole-animal testing paradigm, which needs to be established with at least a **comparable level of confidence**;
- in particular needs to provide a **high level of confidence** when demonstrating the **absence of a relevant risk** of single substances, groups of substances or mixtures to humans and the environment.
- is ideally able to provide **relevant data for a large number of chemicals in a much shorter time**, e.g. by making use of **high-throughput (HT)** technologies;
- can be applied to single **substances, groups** of substances, and **mixtures** of substances;
- should accommodate all relevant risk assessment workflows, including **screening/prioritisation, hazard** identification and characterisation as well as, ultimately, **quantitative risk characterisation**;
- uses up-to-date **exposure assessment and modelling** methodologies to assess exposure from single sources, but also aggregate and cumulative exposure and can be applied in various exposure contexts, including diverse human (e.g. consumers, workers/professionals, general public via the environment) and environmental (e.g. aquatic, terrestrial organisms) exposure contexts, ideally over all stages of a chemical's/product's life cycle;
- is ideally able to provide a **probabilistic** risk characterisation output as a basis for better understanding human health **risk on the population** (including specific sensitive or vulnerable subpopulations) and environmental risks **on the ecosystem level**;

²⁶ This does not preclude that during a transition period, or where NGRA-compliant methodology is not available for certain aspects of CRA, traditional “present generation risk assessment” based on *in vivo* testing may still be performed. It only means that this *in vivo* testing is not part of NGRA itself.

Vision for NGRAroute:

By April 2025 (the end of PARC year 3), NGRAroute will provide a concrete and applicable roadmap proposal for implementing NGRA as the **default approach to chemical risk assessment in EU chemicals legislation**.

By that time, this roadmap will already have been discussed and harmonised as far as possible with all relevant stakeholder groups from the regulatory community (i.e. researchers, risk assessors, risk managers and policy makers, from academia, authorities and industry, in and outside of PARC).

In this vision, “**default approach**” means that NGRA will be the first line of risk assessment, with traditional *in vivo* testing only applied in higher tiers, possibly in a targeted way based on the NGRA outcome, in cases where a) NGRA is not practically feasible or b) the conclusions from NGRA are not sufficiently reliable to safeguard a sufficient protection level for human health or the environment. A similar approach has been introduced in Annex VII of the REACH Regulation for the endpoint skin sensitisation: by default, a set of *in vitro/in chemico* tests (e.g. in the form of a DASS) is required as the first line of risk assessment, but *in vivo* testing still needs to be carried out if the substance to be tested falls outside of the applicability domain of the *in vitro* tests or if these tests do not allow for a clear conclusion on classification and labelling and/or risk assessment.

Scope

The scope of *NGRAroute* encompasses **all relevant²⁷ chemicals legislations** in Europe. Work on the roadmap will be carried out in close **co-operation with partners from other WPs** in PARC, but also with **other currently ongoing EU projects**, such as those organised in the ASPIS cluster²⁸, as well as with all relevant authorities, policy bodies and stakeholders involved in the formal processes established for changing/adapting current legal (e.g. Regulations such as REACH) and sub-legal (e.g. ECHA’s guidance on information requirements and chemical safety assessment under REACH, the SCCS’s Notes of Guidance for the testing of cosmetic ingredients and their safety evaluation SCCS’s, or EFSA’s cross-cutting or sector-specific guidance documents) requirements.

The work on the roadmap will include:

- a research phase on existing conceptual NGRA-related work including existing case studies for its application (already initiated by PARC T2.2, cf. section 6 for details);

²⁷ “All relevant legislation” refers to all legislation, which contains a **hazard/risk assessment workflow of its own** (e.g. REACH, CLP, the Regulations on cosmetics, food additives, or food contact materials, on Occupational Safety and Health etc.).

²⁸ Aside from RISK-HUNT3R, this cluster also includes the projects ONTOX (<https://ontox-project.eu/>) and PrecisionTOX (<https://precisiontox.org/>).

- the development of an “NGRA topology”, by means of which the existing information can be categorised and linked to the diverse aspects of NGRA, such as risk assessment workflows, types of NAMs, or regulatory contexts (already initiated by PARC T2.2);
- the formulation of a generalised NGRA framework (already initiated by the RISK-HUNT3R project/ASPIS cluster and supported by PARC T2.2);
- a systematic analysis of the different parts of the framework, for which solutions already exist, as well as any gaps along with a possible strategy for closing these (supporting and building on the work done in RISK-HUNT3R/ASPIS);
- a strategy for forming science-to-policy (S2PD) networks, which will be used to further develop the roadmap in coordination with the relevant stakeholders, with the goal of identifying where and how the respective legislation texts would need to be amended to implement NGRA as the default approach along with a strategy for how to best implement these amendments;
- the formulation of a work plan for writing and consolidating the roadmap.

The actual practical implementation of the roadmap is not within the scope of Task 2.2, as PARC has no legal mandate in this area. Nevertheless, the S2PD networks established in the course of the roadmap work could become the nucleus for a concerted action by the involved Member States, European agencies and Commission Directorates to initiate the transformation in the respective competent regulatory bodies, enabling them to properly involve affected stakeholder groups. As shown in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.** above, Task 2.2 could also play a coordinative role in this process.

5. NGRA topology

T2.2 is developing a “topology” of the CRA “universe”, which will define how the knowledge around CRA and NGRA will be structured as a basis for further organising the work. For example, it will help conceptualising NGRA, categorising the existing work on the topic, identifying coverage/gaps of existing methodology, pinpointing processes and actors to be addressed under *NGRAroute*. Other PARC activities could benefit from the topology and some are already developing similar schemes. This work is therefore done in close collaboration with the inter-WP working group on semantics set up in December 2022, with which T2.2 is already collaborating. Also, relevant progress in the RISK-HUNT3R project under the ASPIS cluster as well as under other initiatives will be taken into account.

In addition, this work is also highly relevant for building *PARCopedia*, PARC’s knowledge management and community platform (which is also in the remit of PARC Task 2.2 and for which a scoping study is currently under preparation).

In a first attempt to characterise a wider NGRA “topology”, the “NGRA universe” can be grouped into different domains (Figure 2)²⁹.

Figure 2: An initial scheme for dividing the “NGRA Universe” into domains for the purpose of categorising and annotating previous and ongoing NGRA-related work with respect to certain aspects of NGRA, as a basis for supporting the further work on NGRARoute in Task 2.2.

The scheme above is an initial draft that will be further reviewed and developed in the next months of PARC, and by no means represents the final layout of the NGRA domains. In this scheme, any activity or piece of information or knowledge will be associated with one or more of the following domains:

- The chemical domain pertains to substances, substance groups, mixtures, and articles.
- The biological domain encompasses biological systems at different levels of organisation (species/taxa, (sub)populations, organisms, organ, cellular, or molecular systems), related biological or biochemical processes including adverse toxicological effects as organised into “endpoints” (at various hierarchy levels), biological matrices and environmental compartments.
- The actor domain denotes institutions (e.g. EU Member State (MS) government authorities, global organisations, academic institutions) and their roles (e.g. academic researcher, regulatory authority, policy bodies such as the European Parliament),
- The approach domain includes various types of methodologies such as experimental methods and models (e.g., *in vitro* tests acc. to OECD Test Guidelines or the EU Test Method Regulation (EC) 404/2008 (TMR), chemo-analytical methods for determining a specific chemical in a specific matrix or an *in silico* model for predicting the genotoxicity of chemical substances), but also conceptual approaches such as OECD Defined Approaches (DA) or Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATAs).
- The legislative domain addresses the legal context (e.g. REACH or the EU Cosmetics Regulation).

²⁹ Important note to readers: at this stage the following figure and the domains therein represent a first idea and are only meant to make the point. These domains and, in particular, their substructure, will be further elaborated on in the coming weeks and months, inter alia by the inter-WP WG on semantics.

- The risk assessment (and also risk management)³⁰ domain includes all conceptual aspects of CRA, i.e. the CRA workflows for hazard identification (e.g. classification and labelling) and characterisation (e.g. determination of health-based guidance values (HBGVs), exposure assessment and risk assessment as well as the associated problem formulations and risk assessment questions.
- The media domain describes the type (e.g. a report, a podcast etc.) as well as the physical or virtual format (e.g., book, PDF document).

Not all of these domains will be equally relevant for characterising the “NGRA topology” and this will be subject to further exploration in the coming weeks and months.

As an example, a journal article from industry describing an NGRA-based risk assessment of the repeated dose toxicity of chemical “X”, which is used in a cosmetic product, using PBPK modelling and *in vitro* metabolomics data in rat tissue to predict the safety of consumers when using this product, has numerous associations with the domains above, i.e. chemical (substance X), biological (humans, rats, repeat-dose toxicity), approach (PBTK modelling, metabolomics, NGRA scheme), legislative (cosmetics), risk assessment (NGRA workflow), actor (industry, risk assessors) and media (journal article, PDF file).

6. Research on existing NGRA work

To lay the foundation for a roadmap proposal, a comprehensive mapping of existing literature dealing with the conceptual aspects of NGRA, of past and present activities/projects in this field and of the risk assessment workflows installed in current European chemicals legislations has been initiated and is currently ongoing. It is estimated that this part of the work can be concluded around the end of Q2/2023.

Review of existing literature

Aim

The aim of the literature review is to get an overview on the state of the art of NGRA as found in the scientific literature, as a basis for identifying knowledge gaps and new developments in the context of NGRA for human health and the environment. The literature review focuses on publications that have a relevance for the roadmap formulation and development. In this way, maximum use can be made of already existing work, while at the same time avoiding to “reinvent the wheel”.

The resulting reference database will be a living database, which will be updated regularly. New publications and grey literature can be included. It will also be made available to all PARC

³⁰ To prevent misunderstandings: risk management itself is not within the remit or mandate of PARC. However, many aspects of the roadmap will inform risk management, e.g. on the level of protection provided by a specific NGRA workflow, and therefore risk management aspects have to be considered during *NGRAroute* development.

WPs addressing aspects of NGRA in their work and, in this way, will be one of the first resources used collectively by the Partnership.

Methodology

The literature reference management database CITAVI was selected to perform the search. The literature research was conducted from 13 - 16 December 2022. The selected database was PubMed³¹, and pre-selected keywords were used and combined. Duplicate references were subsequently deleted. The main key words included the following search terms: next generation risk assessment, next generation ecological risk assessment, and environmental risk assessment. These main key words were combined with other search terms related either to the overall goals of PARC, like one-health, various regulations, endpoints and approaches or tools. In a next step, exclusion words were selected to focus on the objective and to narrow down the number of references. An overview of the whole approach is provided in Figure 3 (next page).

The initial literature search yielded in total 3709 references published in the years 2015 – 2023 (5212, when considering also earlier years). The database was exported to an Excel file and was uploaded to the ANSES SharePoint to further select manually the relevant references for human health and the environment. For that purpose, each reference received an internal Reference Identity Number and columns were added into the software Microsoft Excel™ to select whether the reference was relevant for human health and/or environmental risk assessment within the scope of *NGRAroute*, or not. An “unclear” assignment was another possible selection option. All references were checked by one reviewer each for human health, and one for the environment. References with “unclear” relevance were always rechecked by a second reviewer, following a “four-eye principle” approach.

³¹ For comparison, ScienceDirect was used in parallel, but resulted in a similar number of references.

Figure 3: Overview of the initial literature search using PubMed

Results and next steps

Consolidation of the database

As of 30 April 2023, the consolidated literature database contains 1001 references from the peer-reviewed literature considered to be relevant within the scope of NGRARoute, i.e. 345 relevant for human health only, 355 for the environment only, and 301 relevant for both.

In the next step, this database will be complemented with references from the private archives of some of the Task 2.2 members. Also partners from other PARC WPs have been asked to contribute their collections. No feedback has been received so far, but it is planned to undertake a second try once the first “full” database has been shared with all of the PARC community. In addition, to complement this search of the peer-reviewed literature with relevant “grey literature”, NGRA-related publications by regulatory authorities and other institutions active in the field of NGRA as well as publicly available reports from relevant research projects will be systemically searched and added.

Categorisation of references

In parallel to the completion of the database, work on categorising the references has begun. Loosely based on the “NGRA topology” domains described in section 5, a set of keywords has been developed to categorise the collected references with respect to their relevance for certain aspects of the NGRARoute work. As an example, if in the further course of the NGRARoute activity specific work is performed on the aspect of the validation of NAMs/NGRA strategies, it is important that all references addressing this aspect are easily identified.

To support and expedite the process of categorisation, a script for the statistical software “R” (R core team, 2022)³² was written to assign the pre-defined key words to the literature references in an automated and objective manner, looking for the respective keywords in the title, abstract and keywords of the respective publication. Meanwhile this script has been successfully applied to the database. In a next step, the result will be evaluated manually for a limited number of references to find out whether in this way, relevant aspects of the references were missed.

Learnings so far

A vast amount of information and knowledge targeting NGRA and future risk assessment is already available within the scientific literature.

Human health NGRA is different from conceivable environmental NGRA approaches (e.g. under the latter several species/taxa need to be considered, the overall ecology as well as biodiversity, climate etc. are important aspects and need to be included). At the same time there also is a lot of overlap, because both areas deal with very similar challenges, ranging from a comprehensive collection of relevant AOP networks to the application of computational models to obtaining insight into the uncertainties associated with the

³² <https://www.r-project.org/> (last accessed 2023-02-15)

traditional approaches. These overlaps or synergies need to be further investigated during the work on the roadmap.

Outlook

While the preparatory literature research work will be complete around the end of Q2/2023 at the latest (likely before), the collection of relevant references will be a continuous process and the reference database will become a living database, which will be made available to all PARC partners as a basis for their work on NGRA-related topics.

Existing past and present projects

NGRA-related projects/activities within and outside of PARC

To avoid duplication of work and use any opportunity for work-sharing and generating synergies, it is essential to gain a good overview of past and present activities on NGRA, both within and outside of PARC.

A map of the PARC projects and activities conducting work relevant to *NGRAroute* was created and made available to the PARC partners on the PARC-internal SharePoint³³. First, the existing project descriptions were screened and projects and activities were listed. Possible synergies were then further discussed during an online meeting held on 19 December 2022, where a total of 25 colleagues from various PARC WPs participated. A follow-up meeting was held in January 2023 with PARC WP 4, 5, 6 and 8 leaders. Overall, the participants, and particularly those from WP6, welcomed the opportunity to collaborate with T2.2 to optimise each other's work.

A Gantt chart reporting the key outputs and timelines of each project relevant to the *NGRAroute* was developed and shared with the respective responsible contact people (Annex II). This or a similar chart will be the basis to foster and maintain the network. A first version has already been made available to the PARC partners via the internal SharePoint³⁴. A list of contacts and a mailing list will be created and shared on the ANSES SharePoint as well, within the dedicated PARC T2.2 folder. Once the *PARCopedia* platform will be up and running (cf. PARC Task 2.2's Deliverable D2.2 which has recently been submitted to the European Commission for review), it is foreseen to create a dedicated space for knowledge sharing and collaboration on all NGRA-related aspects (where, *inter alia*, also the reference list will be shared).

³³ https://agenceanses.sharepoint.com/:w:/r/sites/PARC-ANSES/WP2/Task%202.2/Task%202.2%20projects/02_PARCroute/NGRA_PARC_projects_map/PARC_map_of_NGRAroute_projects_BfR_Kemi_WP4.docx (access only for members of the PARC consortium)

³⁴ https://agenceanses.sharepoint.com/:x:/r/sites/PARC-ANSES/WP2/Task%202.2/Task%202.2%20projects/02_PARCroute/NGRA_PARC_projects_map/Draft_gantt_NGRAroute_projects.xlsx (access only for members of the PARC consortium)

This mapping exercise will be extended further as part of the research work for *NGRAroute*, to also include relevant projects outside of PARC.

Legislation mapping

A legislation mapping exercise was started in December 2022. Rather than starting with a broad overview of all EU legislations, it was decided to begin with a more in-depth analysis of the REACH and CLP legislations, which is currently under revision by T2.2. This legislation contains a number of different processes that cover various CRA workflows from hazard-based identification of Substances of Very High Concern (SVHC) to full quantitative risk characterisation in the context of Chemical Safety Assessment (CSA) and restriction.

The purpose of this analysis is to understand:

- the CRA workflows and associated risk assessment questions posed by the REACH legislation;
- how these questions are addressed for the different human health and environmental endpoints using the current risk assessment paradigm, including an analysis of how an adequate level of protection of humans and the environment is defined and achieved, how confidence in an assessment is acquired, how uncertainties are addressed and what requirements, in particular, need to be fulfilled in order to accept that a chemical substance does not pose a risk to humans or the environment;
- how NAMs can be used in this regulatory environment and what would be the requirements, but also the hurdles for implementing NGRA as the default approach (cf. above for a definition)³⁵;
- who are the relevant key players, i.e. stakeholders involved in this process, that are part of the implementation process and therefore have to be included in the discussions and which regulatory bodies have to be approached in this dialogue, in order to convince them to support the implementation of the aspired change.

At the time of finalising this interim report (end of April 2023), this work is still ongoing. An Excel template for mapping the legislations has been developed and, in a first step, is populated with information on the diverse sub-processes under REACH and CLP: Aside from characterising these sub-processes with respect to their conceptual treatment of hazard, exposure and risk for substances, mixtures and articles, and the role NAMs in this context, particular focus is placed on identifying the relevant actors and their roles in each of these sub-processes, as well as in changing the legal or sub-legal requirements, should that become necessary.

³⁵ Here synergies with PARC Task 6.4 will be explored further.

This table is currently completed by T 2.2 partners from UoB, after which the Excel template will be evaluated and, where necessary, revised, before, in the next step, it will be used to capture all other relevant European chemical legislations. Same as for the literature research, it is hoped that this activity can be concluded around the end of Q2/2023.

It is noted that European legislation is under constant revision. Specifically for the REACH regulation, a proposal of major revisions has been announced by the European Commission for Q4 of 2023. Once the final proposal has been agreed on by all involved parties, the mapping will be adapted accordingly (same as for revisions of any other legislation in scope of this activity).

7. Science-to-Policy Dialogue (S2PD) network

Objective

To support the uptake of the roadmaps developed under *PARCroute*, so-called “Science-to-Policy Dialogue” (S2PD) networks involving actors from both the scientific and policy domains will be created. The goal of installing these networks is to a) recruit expertise from all relevant CRA sub-communities and to b) include a broad spectrum of perspectives in the development of the roadmap and its proper communication (e.g. when to discuss, and with which key actors), to safeguard a similarly broad acceptance of the respective roadmap in the end. In addition, involvement of experts from the regulatory and policy domain will be a key factor, given their role in initiating the necessary steps towards the practical implementation of NGRA into EU chemicals legislation.

Participants of the S2PD network for *NGRARoute*

The S2PD network will involve stakeholders from within and outside of PARC, including members from the EU and outside of the EU, in particular with international organisations such as OECD (see also Figure 1).

General aspects

The S2PD network will be further structured into subnetworks varying in focus and scope, which might be of a standing or *ad hoc* nature, and participation in them will be subject to identified needs. Since each of these networks will pursue a specific goal related to the work under Task 2.2, their co-ordination should lie with Task 2.2. However, for building and maintaining the networks, Task 2.2 will make best use of any possible synergies with WP 3, which is in charge of managing the overall PARC network, including PARC bodies, such as the Stakeholder Forum or the International Board and Governing Board.

In addition to single partners coming from different sectors, including the industry, links and strategic communication will also be established with other existing networks, where possible and useful (e.g. NSC, NORMAN, HESI, etc.).

Status

Task 2.2 has started forming an NGRA network within PARC. Also, a close connection with the RISK-HUNT3R project and the ASPIS cluster was established. This will be gradually expanded, subject to a more detailed plan which will be developed early on in year 2, also based on the findings from the research exercises.

8. NGRARoute timeline

As described in detail above, the work on *NGRARoute* so far focused on the research necessary to map existing literature, activities and legislation in relation to NGRA, and on conceptualising the next steps, *inter alia* to identify needs, gaps and the way forward for writing the roadmap. In addition, networking activities with PARC partners and the RISK-HUNT3R project were successfully initiated, which will be gradually expanded to involve more and more stakeholders in- and outside of PARC, as the *NGRARoute* activity progresses. Figure 4 provides an overview of the general timeline for the *NGRARoute* activity.

Figure 4: General timeline for the *NGRARoute* activity and current status (oval selection; ✓ = finished).